

EXPERIMENTAL AND MODELLING STUDY OF HAIL IMPACT ON COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

Foreign object impact is a serious threat to aircraft, hail or bird impact may seriously degrade the performance of aircraft structures. This work focuses on hail impact experiments and modelling for characterising the impact event and damage initiation in composite material.

Keywords: Hail, Impact, Composite, Experiment, Modelling

INTRODUCTION

As aircraft in general are exposed to various impact scenarios (bird, hail, debris etc.), an understanding of the impact event and the performance of composite materials during impact is important in the development of new structures. This work is focussed on hail impact. Damage due to hail impact may reduce the residual compressive strength of a composite structure significantly. A lot of work have been devoted to the study of solid body impact onto composite materials, e.g. [1,2]. However, the major part of a hail/ice impact can not be considered as a solid body impact [3-5]. The fracture threshold of ice is rather low and the nature of the fracture is fairly brittle. This imposes the necessity to include the fracture behaviour of ice to successfully predict the loading and resulting damage formation in composite materials. The aim of this work is to evaluate the possibility of using finite element modelling with cohesive elements and a simplified analytical model for the hail impact case to predict damage initiation in composite materials. The work is based on experiments and numerical modelling for characterising the ice behaviour and damage initiation of the composite material.

EXPERIMENTS

Materials

Experiments were carried out using ice balls with two different diameters, $\phi = 34$ and 48 mm, manufactured by freezing fresh water in plastic moulds. The moulded ice balls were of rather high quality concerning the presence of cracks, see Figure 1. There were indications of a limited amount of micro-cracks at the position of the plastic mould filling hole. The mass and diameter of each ice ball were measured prior to launch using a scale and a calliper, giving an average density of $\rho_{ice} = 970 \text{ kg/m}^3$. The temperature of the ice during the experiments was $-10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 1. Moulded ice ball.

The composite plates were manufactured using vinyl ester (Norpol DION 9500-501) vacuum infused biaxial carbon fibre non-crimp fabrics (Devold AMT LT450 and DB450, 205 g/m² in each direction). The laminate was quasi-isotropic with a lay-up of $[0^\circ/90^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ]_{s3}$ and a thickness of 5.4 mm. The nominal in-plane dimension of the plates were 250×250 mm. The elastic mechanical properties are collected from [6], see Table 1.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the composite plates. Data from [6].

Property	0°/90°-plies	±45°-plies
Longitudinal Young's modulus, E_{11} [GPa]	100.3	115.6
Transverse Young's modulus, E_{22}, E_{33} [GPa]	7.6	7.6
Shear modulus, G_{12}, G_{13} [GPa]	2.9	2.9
Out of plane shear modulus, G_{23} [GPa]	2.9	2.9
Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}, ν_{13}	0.36	0.36
Poisson's ratio, ν_{23}	0.31	0.31

Test set-up

The impact experiments were conducted using a gas gun consisting of a compression tank connected to a steel pipe approximately 5 meters long with an inner diameter of 52 mm. The end of the pipe was placed inside a box where the plates were fastened approximately 200 mm from the pipe end using a steel rig, see Figures 2 and 3. The steel rig was made of three parts, front and back plates, width and height 300 mm and 20 mm thick with a steel spacer in between. The plates were mounted in the rig using steel bolts with a plexi-glass strip in front and a polyethylene (PE) strip in the back of the plates, see Figure 4. The polymer strips were 5 mm thick and the clamping was made to compress the PE strip approximately 1 mm. The open window measured 200×200 mm with a radius of 10 mm in the corners.

A low density cylindrical foam plug (sabot) was used to push the ice balls down the pipe using the compressed air. The foam plugs were used to soften the acceleration and protect the ice. The impact speed was measured using two laser sensors placed at a specific distance between each other close to the pipe end, see Fig. 3.

Figure 2. Complete test setup.

Figure 3. Steel rig with plate and pipe end.

Figure 4. Centre cross-section of the steel rig, view from above.

A strain gauge (Kyowa KFRP-2-120-C1-3L1M3R, 2 mm gauge length, 120 Ω) was applied in the centre on the back of the plates. The gauge was applied in the direction of the surface ply fibre direction. The strain was registered using a half bridge amplifier with a bandwidth of 100 kHz. The centre deflection and strain were registered using a sampling frequency of 1 MHz. The impact events were recorded using high speed video (MotionPro X3 Plus, Red Lake) using a sampling frequency of approximately 6000 frames per second.

NUMERICAL MODEL

The numerical modelling part was divided into calibrating the ice material model and modelling the threshold velocity for initiation of damage (delamination). All calculations were carried out using LS-Dyna.

The calibration of the ice material model was performed by choosing a representative material model and a parameter fitting procedure. Two experiments were chosen to calibrate the model, one using a $\phi 34$ mm ice ball and one using a $\phi 50$ mm ice ball. The velocity in both tests was beneath the delamination initiation threshold velocity. A factorial parameter study was performed to identify how the material model parameters influenced the impact response. The factorial study was followed by a fitting of the parameters to the experimental results.

The plate was modelled using layered thick shell elements for the plate and Smooth Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) for the ice ball. Four layers of thick shell elements (6 plies in each element layer) were used through the thickness of the plate.

The modelling of damage initiation during impact was performed in a similar way as in the calibration study except that a solid cohesive element layer (thickness $t_{coh} = 0.01$ mm) was included in the centre of the laminate. Figure 5 illustrates the FE model.

Figure 5. FE model of the ice impact, a) Complete model, b) Close up of the ball and the centre of the plate.

The material properties for the cohesive layer were estimated using published experimental values. No references were found for the energy release rates, G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} , for carbon fibre NCF and toughened vinylester. However, one reference was found for a glass fibre weave and a toughened vinylester [7] and it was decided that the material system was reasonably representative for the present work. The material properties are presented in Table 2. The stiffness of the cohesive layer was based on the thickness of the cohesive layer and the out-of-plane stiffness of the laminate.

The value of the peak tractions of the material model is a delicate matter, experimental tests are complicated and often only a qualified guess can be made. Values of toughened vinylesters from published articles [8,9] and material data specifications [10] were found ranging between $\sigma_{t,max} = 20 - 76$ MPa and $\tau_{s,max} = 20 - 85$ MPa for the tensile and interlaminar shear strength, respectively. Values of $N = 50$ MPa and $T = 75$ MPa were chosen as representative peak tractions for the composite used in this work. The values for N and G_{Ic} are, however, not critical as an analysis of the results confirmed that delamination is Mode II dominated.

Table 2. Material properties used for the cohesive material model. Data from [7].

Property	Value
Energy release rate in mode I, G_{Ic} [J/m ²]	577 ^[7]
Energy release rate in mode II, G_{IIc} [J/m ²]	1152 ^[7]
Peak traction in normal direction, N [MPa]	50
Peak traction in tangential direction, T [MPa]	75

The modelling of the damage initiation threshold velocity was performed for four different ice ball diameters, $\phi 25$, $\phi 34$, $\phi 40$ and $\phi 48$ mm. Experimental results were only available for the $\phi 34$ and $\phi 48$ mm ice ball impacts, the other two were performed to give a more thorough comparison with the analytical model.

ANALYTICAL MODEL

Fundamental relations

Figure 6 illustrates a crushing ice ball of radius R , density ρ_i and velocity V_0 impacting a plate of thickness h , density ρ_p and effective plate stiffness D^* . The plate locally deflects with a velocity \dot{w} and interacts with the ice ball within a radius c .

Figure 6. Geometry of ice ball interacting with a plate

For short impact times the flexural waves in a plate propagate without interaction with the boundaries. If shearing is neglected the deflection velocity \dot{w} under a distributed load is bound between zero and the deflection velocity under a point load F [11]:

$$0 \leq \dot{w} \leq \dot{w}_{\max} \quad \text{where} \quad \dot{w}_{\max} = \frac{1}{8} F / \sqrt{\rho_p h D^*} \quad (1)$$

The delamination threshold load F_{th} for a concentrated load in this kind of impact is bound between the threshold load for the static case with $\dot{w}=0$ and an upper bound for $\dot{w} = \dot{w}_{\max}$ [12]:

$$F_{d1}^{stat} \leq F_{th} \leq F_{d1}^{dyn} \quad \text{where} \quad F_{d1}^{stat} = F_{d1} \quad F_{d1}^{dyn} = C F_{d1} \quad C \approx 1.213 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{and} \quad F_{d1} = \pi \sqrt{32 D^* G_{IIc} / 3} = \pi \sqrt{8 Q_f^* G_{IIc} / 9} \quad \text{with} \quad Q_f^* = 12 D^* / h^3$$

G_{IIc} is the critical strain energy release rate in mode II delamination. The lower bound is also lower than the threshold load for a more distributed load. In the current model we will model the crushing ice ball as a cloud of particles, i.e. with negligible cohesive forces and no retardation during the impact. The resulting load is obtained by multiplying the dynamic pressure p from the mass flow within the area of contact:

$$F = p \pi c^2 = \pi c^2 \rho_i (V_0 - \dot{w})^2 / 2 \leq \pi c^2 \rho_i V_0^2 / 2 \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{F} = \pi \rho_i c (V_0 - \dot{w}) [\dot{c}(V_0 - \dot{w}) - c \ddot{w}]$$

Dots indicate differentiation with respect to time. Extreme values of F are obtained for $\dot{F} = 0$. The minimum load $F=0$ is obtained for $c=0$ or $V_0 = \dot{w}$, while the maximum load is obtained by setting the square bracket in Eq. (3) to zero.

Lower bound for threshold velocity

A lower bound for the delamination threshold velocity V_{th} is obtained by combining the upper bound for the peak impact load with a lower bound for the delamination threshold load F_{th} , which corresponds to setting $\dot{w}=0$. The peak load in this case is obtained for $c=R$. Combining Eqs (2) and (3) for $\dot{w}=0$ and $c=R$ and solving for V_{th} gives:

$$V_{th} \geq 2\sqrt{\sqrt{2Q_f^* h^3 G_{IIc}} / (3\rho_i)} / R \quad (4)$$

Upper bound for threshold velocity

An upper bound for the delamination threshold velocity V_{th} is obtained by combining the lower bound of the peak impact load with the upper bound for the delamination threshold load F_{th} . In this case w agrees with the upper bound in (1), which implies that $\dot{w}=0$ when $\dot{F}=0$. Thus, the maximum load is obtained for $c=0$, i.e. for the maximum contact radius $c=R$. Insertion of this condition into Eq. (3a) and use of the relation in Eq. (1) results in the following equation:

$$V_{th}^2 - 2\frac{F_{th}}{8\sqrt{\rho_p h D^*}} V_0 + \frac{F_{th}^2}{64\rho_p h D^*} - \frac{2F_{th}}{\pi\rho_i R^2} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Equating the threshold load F_{th} in Eq. (5) with the upper bound delamination threshold load CF_{d1} in Eq. (2) results in the following threshold velocity V_{th} :

$$V_{th} \leq C\pi\sqrt{G_{IIc}/(6\rho_p h)} \begin{pmatrix} + \\ - \end{pmatrix} 2\sqrt{C\sqrt{2Q_f^* h^3 G_{IIc}} / (3\rho_i)} / R \quad (6)$$

The first term in Eq. (6) accounts for the reduced relative velocity between the ice ball and plate due to mobility of a plate under a concentrated load. Consideration of the finite contact pressure distribution will reduce the magnitude of this term. The second term is identical to Eq. (4), except for the additional constant C , which accounts for the increased threshold load due to inertial effects in a mobile plate. The negative sign was discarded, as it produces negative roots.

RESULTS

The ice model behaviour is very similar to what was registered in the experiments, a pressure wave forms at the point of contact and moves towards the back of the ice ball. The wave creates micro cracks which suddenly transforms the ice from a solid body to a body made up of small ice particles. A small rise in the strain response can be seen just prior to when the equator of the ball reaches the plate, which is probably related to the momentum of the ball. Figures 7 to 8 illustrate the impact scenario. The pictures in Figure 7a should be read from the first column on the left going down, second column going up etc. Figure 7b shows a snapshot of the pressure wave travelling from the impact point.

Figure 7. Pictures captured by high speed camera, a) Impact event, b) Pressure wave in the ice.

Figure 8. Pictures from simulation of the $\phi 48$ mm ice impact.

A comparison between the experimental and numerical results for the ice impacts below the delamination threshold velocity is presented in Figures 9 and 10.

Figure 9. Comparison between experimental and numerical response for $\phi 34$ mm ice impact below damage initiation threshold velocity, centre strain.

Figure 10. Comparison between experimental and numerical values for $\phi 48$ mm ice impact below damage initiation threshold velocities, centre strain.

The numerical results for delamination threshold velocities are presented together with the experimental values in Table 3. The velocity in the first impact scenario did not reach the delamination threshold velocity in the experiment.

Table 3. Numerical and experimental values for delamination threshold velocities.

Test scenario	Experimental [m/s]	FE [m/s]
5.4 mm plate, $\phi 25$ mm ice ball	-	194
5.4 mm plate, $\phi 34$ mm ice ball	136 - 152	147
5.4 mm plate, $\phi 40$ mm ice ball	-	128
5.4 mm plate, $\phi 48$ mm ice ball	>97	111

A comparison between FE predictions and experimental results with the upper and lower bounds of the analytical model is given in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Comparison between delamination velocity from FE and experiments with analytical upper and lower bounds

DISCUSSION

The analytical model for ice impact provides relatively tight bounds on the delamination threshold velocity, and is validated by the predictions of the numerical model, which all lie within the analytical bounds. The numerical model is significantly more time consuming but provides more complete information about the various phenomena during ice impact, and allows for more complex geometries and boundary conditions.

A common weakness of both models is the neglect of matrix cracks, which may influence the onset of delamination. Material strain rate effects were also neglected in both models. Further studies are required to clarify the importance of these effects. The most obvious limitation of the analytical model is the assumption of a concentrated contact load, and it is likely that the model could be improved by consideration of a finite contact area.

The experimental results indicate that the numerical and analytical models are valid for prediction of delamination induced by ice impact, but the limited number of tests and lack of reliable material data prevent a full experimental validation.

There are several uncertainties connected to the experiments and material properties which may affect the outcome of the results significantly. Both the ice and composite material may have a large variation in the controlling material strength or critical energy properties which may or may not be strain-rate dependent. The FE model displays a strong effect on the delamination threshold velocity for the assumed peak tangential traction, T . The value used here was only estimated from a wide range of published values for the interlaminar shear strength of mostly different compositions of matrix and reinforcement. An experimental value for the material in this study would be required to give a stronger support for the applicability of the numerical modelling strategy.

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